

BIAS

Mitigating biases
of AI in the
labour market

Deliverable 7.2

Revised dissemination, exploitation, communications plan

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Revised dissemination, exploitation, communications plan

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Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CBR	Case-based Reasoning
D7.1	Deliverable 7.1
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication
D&C	Dissemination & Communication
DoA	Description of Action
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESF+	European Social Fund Plus
ESIF	European Structural and Investment Funds
HR	Human Resources
HRM	Human Resources Management
IP	Intellectual Properties
IRL	Investor Readiness Level
IRR	Internal Rate of Return
JTF	Just Transition Fund
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
M3	Month 3
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NLP	Natural Language Processing
Q&A	Questions & Answers
ROE	Return on Equity
ROI	Return on Investment
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SMA s	Social Media Accounts
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise
SoMe	Social Media
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
WP	Work Package

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2 Executive Summary

This deliverable aims to present an updated version of the dissemination, exploitation, and communication strategy, along with the associated actions that will be implemented during the BIAS project. This document also provides an overview of the actions implemented during the first year of the project, compared to the initial version of the dissemination and communication plan (D7.1 – Month 3). It builds on the original strategy set in M3, evaluating the activities undertaken in the first year of the project and describing the focus of dissemination during the third and fourth years.

The leader of WP7 (LOBA) is responsible for:

- The overall management and support of the activities defined under the present dissemination and communication plan, and for developing the main tools and materials to be used for the implementation of the plan.
- Monitoring the dissemination and communication activities, assessing performance, and identifying necessary corrective measures.

All partners will also be actively involved in carrying out the assigned dissemination and communication actions and are highly committed to ensuring a satisfactory dissemination of the project results. In general, the partners' expected contributions are to:

- Support the communication and dissemination of the project with activities in their own countries among their contacts and networks.
- Provide news and updates for the website and newsletter.
- Participate in events and promote the project at them.
- Help keep the project's social media accounts (SMAs) active by suggesting and providing relevant content to be posted on BIAS social media by LOBA, and by posting relevant content about the project on their own channels, mentioning @BIASProjectEU.

3 Introduction

This document represents the deliverable "Revised Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communications Plan," which is part of WP7 Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication (DEC) activities: Mitigating Bias in AI in the Labour Market. The plan will serve as a useful guide for the partners to ensure effective and satisfactory dissemination and communication of the project's activities and results during the third and fourth years of the action's implementation.

The present report outlines:

- The new objectives of the DEC Plan & Strategy.
- The new internal workflow of WP7.
- An evaluation of what was promised in the DEC plan versus what was achieved during the first two years of the project.
- An overview of the performance of the dissemination and communication activities implemented during the first two years of the project and an evaluation of these two years' KPIs.
- Updates to the strategy in terms of channels and tools, networking and clustering, project and community sustainability, post-project Trustworthy AI Helix maintenance, and funding synergies for exploitation.
- Validation of the initial timeline and presentation of the timeline for the third year of the project.

4 BIAS in a nutshell

BIAS is a four-year project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme, that will empower the Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Human Resources Management (HRM) community by addressing algorithmic biases and mitigating them.

Because AI is increasingly deployed in the labour market to recruit, train, and engage employees or monitor for infractions that can lead to disciplinary proceedings, the BIAS project is investigating its use in the labour market. The project is also studying how human and societal biases are potentially reproduced in AI-based systems and developing tools to identify and mitigate these biases. BIAS is doing this through a 3-pronged empirical research methodology and an impact strategy:

- **The research strategy involves:**
 - The creation in each country of National Labs (communities of practitioners, employees, HRM, and AI specialists with a special focus on marginalised people/communities that will be involved in the co-creation and all other engagement activities of BIAS), a needs analysis, stakeholder involvement (by resorting to surveys and interviews to AI developers and HR [Human Resources] executives) and co-creation workshops.
 - The creation of a proof-of-concept for innovative technology based on Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Case-Based Reasoning (CBR) for use in an HR recruitment use case. The system will contain two modules: one for bias detection and another for bias mitigation.
 - An ethnographic fieldwork, with employers, employees, and AI developers from different European countries providing richly textured information about current experiences and future imaginaries of bias and AI in employment settings to PhDs and researchers.
- **The impact strategy involves:**
 - Capacity-building Sessions.
 - Awareness-raising Events.
 - Networking and clustering both online and in physical events.
 - Open access scientific publications.
 - Launch of open-source code.
 - A viable commercialisation strategy (including a market analysis and commercialisation roadmap; and initial explorations of regulatory acceptability).

BIAS is composed of 9 leading partners (from 9 different countries) in the areas of i) AI solutions, ii) SSH (Social Sciences and Humanities) knowledge, iii) diversity, iv) dissemination and communication, v) gender equality in HR practices and vi) industrial uptake and commercialization.

In total, the consortium is made up of 4 universities, 3 communication partners, 1 large industrial organisation and 1 SME. One partner, Bern University of Applied Sciences, is an Associated Partner.

The specific objectives of the project are to:

- Develop trustworthy, novel tools for bias identification and bias mitigation in AI/NLP systems that can be deployed across multiple applications.
- Engage in robust stakeholder engagement and co-creation, especially targeting marginalised people/communities, for the creation of the Debiaser in the specific use case of recruitment.
- Empower the AI and HRM community through capacity building to develop better technology and institute better practices by integrating concerns about bias into their everyday workflow and strategic considerations. Raise awareness among specialists and the public about the importance of addressing algorithmic bias.
- Gain a richly detailed understanding of bias in recruitment and HRM, especially as it relates to the use of AI and technology, that advances the field of worker studies as well as making capacity-building activities more relevant and informing future trajectories of NLP and AI research.
- Make hiring practices less biased through the development of a proof-of-concept system that can be further developed into a commercially viable product to reduce bias in AI systems used in recruitment.

BIAS will focus on four priorities, with which the project is highly aligned by its overarching strategy of the work programme:

- Digital Agenda.
- Artificial Intelligence.
- Co-programmed European Partnerships.
- Social Sciences and Humanities.

5 Updated Dissemination, Exploitation and Communications Plan & Strategy

The DEC strategy has been devised with one main goal in mind: achieving the greatest possible impact within the allocated budget envelope among the identified target groups.

During these two years, the first two stages of this strategy were successfully achieved (Stage 0 – Knowledge and Stage 1 – BIAS Strategy). In its first year, when the project had just started and there was not much content yet from the project's activities, the communication strategy focused on establishing appropriate conditions for successful dissemination. This included conducting a situational analysis of the project (Stage 0) and developing the initial strategy, defining a unique identity for the project, setting up relevant tools and channels to be used, and starting to create awareness about the project, thereby building a community of stakeholders and target groups (Stage 1). During this phase, we primarily worked on the base of the marketing funnel, focusing on **notoriety** (awareness). As soon as the first findings and results emerged from project activities, the objective of dissemination shifted towards ensuring that these were communicated through the project's channels.

Currently, the project is undergoing **Stage 2 – Action Plan**, which includes the detailed planning of all communication activities for Stage 0 and Stage 1 of the BIAS campaign in a systematic manner. This involves:

- **Creation of actions:** Creative definition of the communication action and the briefing on how this will be put into practice.
- **Definition of objectives:** Contextualization of the action in terms of how each action/message will be adapted to suit any target audience.
- **Assignment of responsibilities:** Defining and assigning the responsible party for each action.
- **Timing:** Defining the period of the action based on prior coordination with the other WPs.
- **Materials:** Defining the communication materials to be created.

During this stage, the project sought to deepen the audience's **affinity**, fostering a stronger interest and engagement by showcasing preliminary results, increasing web traffic, and actively managing social media presence. This phase is critical for engaging stakeholders and building a community around the project.

In the third year, our efforts will pivot towards **conversion**. This involves transforming the awareness and interest generated thus far into tangible actions. We will encourage stakeholders to actively engage with the project's resources and participate in events, discussions, and other activities. This stage is critical for driving deeper involvement and commitment from our target groups, converting their interest into active participation and use of the project's outputs.

As the project approaches its final year, the focus will shift to creating **loyalty**. Here, the goal is to solidify the relationships we have built, ensuring that stakeholders remain engaged and continue to benefit from the project's outcomes, even after BIAS is finished. This phase will emphasize reinforcing the value of the project's results, fostering long-term loyalty, and encouraging continued support and advocacy among our audience.

By carefully transitioning through these stages, from building initial awareness and establishing a strong project identity to driving active engagement and ensuring sustained interest, the DEC strategy aims to achieve its overarching goal of maximizing impact within the budget and among identified target groups.

5.1. WP7 modus operandi

The WP7 – Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation is led by LOBA and supported by Crowdhelix. This collaboration adds significant value to the dissemination, communication, and exploitation efforts. However, all partners have Person Months allocated to WP7, indicating that they should also actively participate in all tasks.

As the leader of WP7, LOBA has established internal actions and workflows to ensure successful cooperation among all elements involved. These actions/initiatives are as follows:

- **Biweekly Meetings with Crowdhelix:** These 30-minute meetings enable LOBA to track the status of tasks 7.3, 7.4, and 7.5. They also provide an opportunity for brainstorming and defining the next steps for WP7.
- **Weekly Meetings with NTNU:** Organized by NTNU, these 30-minute meetings allow both the coordination team and LOBA to discuss ongoing topics or clarify aspects pending approval and feedback from both sides.
- **BIAS Communication Helpdesk:** On the first Tuesday of every month, LOBA is available online for 30 minutes (extendable based on partners' needs). The objective of this helpdesk is for LOBA to stay updated on partners' upcoming activities, have direct and efficient discussions on their needs, and understand how LOBA can best support them.
- **Reporting Procedure:** To ensure successful dissemination of the BIAS project and an efficient reporting process within the participant portal, partners are required to fill in an Excel sheet for monitoring communication and dissemination activities and their impact. Additionally, LOBA has created a form that partners can use whenever they have a Dissemination & Communication (D&C) action to communicate. This facilitates LOBA in obtaining all the necessary information to implement effective promotional actions.

6 Overview of the BIAS activities & performance until M24

6.1. Evaluation of initial framework set up for the dissemination and communication

The following table presents the main components of the initial dissemination & communication plan, including the evaluation criteria for assessing the success of each item.

COMPONENT	DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION PLAN	EVALUATION OF THE FIRST TWO YEARS
IDENTITY	<p>The identity comprises the noticeable elements of a brand (for instance - trademark colour, logo, name, symbol). It's what identifies and differentiates a brand in the target audience's mind.</p> <p>Identity guidelines were also created, to help all contributing counterparts to stay close to the BIAS identity and work as supporting material for the daily creation of dissemination and communication materials.</p>	<p>The identity created for BIAS provided a cohesive visual identity for the project. All elements of the BIAS identity have been used appropriately and successfully implemented in all materials produced in the project such as templates, brochures, website, posters, roll-up, banners, videos, etc.</p>
CORE MESSAGES/CLAIMS	<p>The main claim used by the project: "Mitigating biases of AI in the labour market".</p> <p>Core message/mission: "AI used in the labour market needs to be trustworthy and socially responsible."</p>	<p>Both the claim and core message are effective. The keywords used are simple and familiar to the general audience, promoting inclusivity in the communication. The message includes a call to action, highlighting the urgency and importance of the project while drawing attention to the target audiences.</p> <p>The claim has been successfully integrated into various dissemination and communication materials, such as brochures and the website.</p>
TARGET GROUPS	<p>Key Players</p> <p>Specific platforms using AI systems to analyse data - LinkedIn, Indeed, itForte, Dice, Angel.co, Authentic Jobs, naukri.com.</p> <p>New technologies developers.</p> <p>Public and private investors.</p> <p>Context Settlers</p> <p>Policy makers at international level - EU Agency for Fundamental Rights,</p>	<p>The list of target groups defined for the project is exhaustive. For each group, the project has defined target profiles, interests, pain points, added value, and key messages to use.</p> <p>Taking this into account, the project has the capacity to provide diverse content tailored to the relevance for each target group. Going forward, dedicated campaigns, actionable</p>

**CHANNELS &
TOOLS**

UN Industrial Development Organization, European Social Fund Standardization Organizations - CEN and CENELEC.

Professional networks and platforms for both businesses and employees – European Association of People Management, International Labour Organization, Business Europe, European Trade Union Confederation.

Advocates

Individual workers, such as those engaged in co-creation workshops and ethnographic interviews.

Educators, both secondary and higher education.

Citizen groups and advocacy organizations - ILGA- Europe (LGBTQ+ organization for Europe and Central Asia), European Network Against Racism, Algorithmic Justice League, Age Platform Europe.

Academics, researchers, and think tanks - Center for Intersectional Justice, Future Advocacy AI Think Tank, Global Partnership on Artificial Intelligence, Algorithm Watch.

Website.

- Social media (Facebook, X, LinkedIn, Instagram, Telegram).
- Events organised by the project:

> Co-creation Workshops

> Capacity-building Sessions

> Awareness-raising Sessions

> AI Fairness Inaugural Conference

- External events where the project partners participate to spread the word about BIAS and its achievements.
- Scientific publications.
- Media publication in media outlets.
- Email marketing
- Trustworthy AI Helix
- Communication toolkit, promotional materials and merchandising.
- Project presentation
- Promotional videos

knowledge, materials, tools, and videos were and will be implemented to address each different target group. Finally, a mapping of local, national, and European actors belonging to the identified target groups was conducted at the beginning of the project, allowing LOBA to better understand the stakeholders it needs to engage with.

- A splash page was created in M3, originating awareness at an early stage. The official website was launched in Month 5, and it has been regularly updated since then.
- Social media (X, Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, Telegram) have been regularly updated with at least 2 posts per week plus additional shares and retweets (245 posts were published in X, 246 in Facebook, 275 in LinkedIn, 69 in Instagram and 7 in Telegram). The social media content had successfully directed traffic to the website.

EXCEL FOR MONITORING

The monitoring and reporting excel is a shared document where partners are requested to update the information related with the

Partners have used this monitoring and reporting procedure during the first two

- Partners have participated in 51 external events.
- 4 scientific publications have been made.
- One PR was launched in May 2023 announcing the kick start of the project to 599 journalists (having 178 unique opens and 4 links opened). Another PR was launched in September 2024 announcing the National Labs initiative to 758 journalists (having 252 unique opens and 5 links opened).
- BIAS has released 2 newsletters and 14 mass mailings about specific topics of the project.
- 41 publications (from the BIAS project and other stakeholders) have been done under the Trustworthy AI Helix.
- BIAS has created an initial communication kit (composed of Word and PPT templates, folders, letterhead paper, etc.), promotional material (composed of brochures, flyers, roll-up, etc.), and merchandising (composed of anti-stress balls, pens, etc.).
- One institutional presentation of the project is available to support the presentation of the project in participation in events.
- A promotional video is also available in YouTube with more than 135 views.
- Other 37 videos were created by the project.

PERFORMANCE AND REPORTING	<p>dissemination activities implemented. The excel is divided into these spreadsheets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination activities: Those that have a stronger focus on disseminating knowledge and results towards its actual use, in a targeted manner to specific beneficiaries or potential end-users, i.e. knowledge transfer, scientific publications, use or replicability of results/methodologies, lessons learned, data, etc. • Communication activities: Those that are aimed at promoting the action and its results. These activities require strategic and targeted measures for communicating about i) the action and ii) its results to a multitude of audience, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. • Scientific Publications: To be filled in at the time of publication. 	<p>years and they will continue to use it throughout the project. Occasional reminders have been and will be sent to partners to keep the information updated. The Excel has recently been revamped, to make it easier and more intuitive to fill in.</p>
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Table 1: Evaluation of initial framework set up for the dissemination and communication

6.2. Key performance indicators of the 2nd year

This section presents an overview of the performance of the dissemination and communication activities implemented during the first two years of the project (November 2022 – 18 October 2024). Table 2 shows the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) compared to the current status. These KPIs align with the overall project KPIs stipulated in the Description of Action (DoA) and D7.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan. This information will help assess necessary improvements or adjustments to the strategy.

TOOLS & CHANNELS	METRIC METHOD	EXPECTED RESULTS IN TOTAL AT M24	2 ND YEAR RESULTS (M1 – M24)	STATUS
WEBSITE	Website user	1500	8,516	✔
	Total page views	5000	30,951	✔

	Countries reached	10	108	✓
PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS	Number distributed at events and meetings	1,000	3,000	✓
FACTSHEETS	Factsheets produced	3	2	⚠
SOCIAL MEDIA (SOME)	Total Followers	500	1,272	✓
	Posts	60	835	✓
	Clicks to the website through SoMe posts	100	3,441	✓
PRESS RELEASES	Press releases distributed	2	2	✓
NEWSLETTERS AND MAILING LIST	Mailing list subscribers	300	417	✓
	Newsletters sent	2	2	✓
	Newsletter views (in website)	150	110	⚠
	National lab e-mails	5	5	✓
PROMOTIONAL VIDEOS	Number of videos	3	38	✓
	Views: YouTube, SoMe, website	500	1,814	✓
	# of events presented at	4	47	✓
SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS, WHITE PAPERS	Papers published or submitted	4	4	✓
POPULAR MEDIA ARTICLES	Number of articles published	30	40	✓
EXTERNAL EVENTS	Number of events attended to disseminate the project	8	47	✓
CLUSTERING WITH RELATED PROJECTS	No. of projects liaised with	>10	14	✓

Table 2: Progress against the KPIs

7 Updates to the DEC

7.1. Channels and tools updates

This section describes the updates to the channels and tools initially planned under D7.1, as well as new approaches for the third year of the project. During the project meetings in Venice (December 2023) and Porto (June 2024), the consortium conducted brainstorming sessions to identify key outcomes and results of the project and to explore ways to disseminate them in more accessible formats. The insights from these sessions have been incorporated into this section.

7.1.1. Website

As we move into the conversion phase of our marketing funnel, the website will become even more central to our strategy. Having established a strong foundation during the first two years, where traffic exceeded expectations, our focus now shifts towards leveraging this platform to convert interest into concrete actions and engagement.

In the upcoming year, we expect a significant increase in website traffic driven by the wealth of new content and events, including the online round of Co-creation Workshops, Awareness-raising Sessions, Capacity-building Sessions, and the highlight event, the Summer School. These events and their results will be prominently featured on the website, providing valuable resources and insights that encourage deeper engagement from our target audiences.

The website will also serve as a hub for showcasing key findings from work packages 2 to 6. We will develop and display factsheets, infographics, and short videos that effectively communicate the project's results and benefits. This not only enhances transparency and accessibility but also motivates stakeholders to take the next step, whether it's participating in an event, subscribing to our communications, or implementing the project's findings in their own work. As an example, to facilitate the process of subscribing the BIAS newsletter, a pop-up subscription window will be added on the website to encourage this action. Furthermore, the consortium aims to present more articles highlighting AI's impact on work life and promoting diversity, equity, and inclusion. These articles will also cover key conclusions from the project's activities, making them valuable resources for our audience.

Additionally, direct traffic to the website will be bolstered through strategic use of social networks, ensuring that our messages reach a wide audience. By highlighting specific project actions and initiatives through dedicated pages and targeted content, we aim to foster a stronger connection with our stakeholders, guiding them through the funnel from awareness and interest to active participation and conversion.

7.1.2. Social media channels

To effectively transition into the conversion phase of the marketing funnel, the social media strategy will be instrumental in driving tangible actions from the audience, such as participating in events, utilizing project tools, and engaging more deeply with the project's content.

In the third year of the project, the social media channels will play a pivotal role in this process. The management of these channels will adhere to a detailed plan ensuring consistent engagement with at least two posts per week, supplemented by shares, retweets, and targeted paid campaigns. This approach will enhance the visibility of key content and foster a more active connection with the audience.

To drive conversions, social media efforts will focus on:

1. **Increased engagement and action-oriented content**

- **Promoting internal activities and events:** Social media posts should not only inform but also actively encourage participation in events like Capacity-building Sessions, Co-creation Workshops, Awareness-raising Sessions, Summer School 2025, and Helix Events. Posts should include compelling calls-to-action (CTAs) such as "Register now," "Join us live," or "Sign up today," linking directly to registration pages or event details. For example, recap videos of external events where partners participated can be created to share knowledge with the community. Additionally, leveraging social media ads can help target specific demographics most likely to convert.
- **Showcasing key takeaways and insights:** Posts sharing insights from mapping, surveys, and expert interviews should include CTAs that drive followers to read full reports, subscribe to newsletters, or download resources from the website. This approach turns passive readers into active participants and subscribers. To boost engagement and conversions, the social media strategy will incorporate Reels featuring dynamic subtitles, infographics, and direct messages from consortium partners. These Reels will provide quick, engaging insights into project activities and results, encouraging viewers to visit the website and participate in events. On Instagram, the goal is to share knowledge by posting impactful statistics and articles, using polls to generate interaction, and organizing stories into highlight folders.

2. **Interactive content to drive conversion**

- **Interactive campaigns:** Launch interactive campaigns, such as live Q&A sessions, polls, or quizzes related to understanding and mitigating bias. These activities can direct users to the project's tools, like the Debiaser, encouraging them to try the tool themselves.

- **Testimonials and case studies:** Share stories and testimonials from participants of previous workshops or users of the Debiaser tool, highlighting how these have positively impacted their work or understanding of bias. Such posts can include CTAs encouraging others to join upcoming sessions or use the tool.
3. **Leveraging YouTube for conversion**
- **Focused video content:** While YouTube serves primarily as a video repository, strategically curated playlists or featured videos can be used to guide viewers towards specific actions, such as attending events or engaging with the project's outputs. Videos should end with strong CTAs directing viewers to learn more on the project website, sign up for updates, or participate in specific initiatives.
 - **Highlighting new content:** Announce new videos, such as expert interviews or awareness-raising content, across all social media channels, encouraging followers to visit the YouTube channel. Ensure these announcements include a summary of the video's content and a direct link to the YouTube video, with a CTA encouraging further engagement.

Although the **First Followers** paid campaign yielded positive results, as outlined in D7.3 - Report on Dissemination Activities, there remains room for improvement through additional targeted paid advertising. These campaigns will focus on two key areas:

- **Facebook:** Between October 2024 and August 2025, the campaign will aim to increase the number of newsletter subscribers. Since engagement on this social media channel has been more challenging, the campaign will focus on attracting new users while converting them into subscribers.
- **Instagram:** From October 2024 to July 2025, this campaign will concentrate on growing the number of followers and enhancing engagement with posts. As Instagram is the most recent social media platform adopted by BIAS, this effort will help establish a stronger presence, encouraging sustained interaction and audience growth.

7.1.3. Videos

LOBA will produce the remaining two awareness-raising videos: "How is Bias Experienced?" (Month 26) and "How to Recognize Bias" (Month 32). Additionally, recordings of BIAS participation in future external events and activities will be made available. Other videos will also be created to promote internal events, such as the BIAS Summer School and the recordings of the Awareness-raising Webinars.

All these videos will be published on the BIAS YouTube channel and shared across the project's social media channels. To enhance the visibility and discoverability of these videos, BIAS will create strategic thumbnails and titles optimized for Search Engine Optimization (SEO). These elements are

designed to capture attention and improve searchability, ensuring that the videos reach a broader audience effectively.

7.1.4. Communication toolkit

If necessary, changes and improvements will be made to the communication toolkit already existent. The brochure, flyer, roll-up, and poster can be adapted according to the new needs and updates of the project. However, for the sake of sustainability, keeping in mind that the materials that compose this communication toolkit were already printed and distributed among the partners, it should be avoided to change these materials.

7.1.5. Press Releases

Over the next two years, at least three additional press releases will be strategically issued to highlight key project milestones, results, and events. Until now, our media engagement has focused on building awareness and affinity, introducing our project's name and mission. As we shift towards conversion, we will increase our media outreach. LOBA will use an established database of approximately 800 journalists, tailored to specific results and audiences, to ensure broad and effective dissemination. Partners will also be encouraged to share press releases in their native languages with relevant media in their regions.

7.1.6. Newsletters & mass mailing

BIAS distributes a newsletter every seven months. Until the end of the project, four more newsletters will be sent to its list of subscribers. Each newsletter will clearly communicate the project's main news, events, activities, and results. They may include articles, interviews, videos, and infographics and will be uploaded to the public section of the website.

To complement the newsletter distribution, the project will also send mass mailings with relevant announcements or achievements, such as registration for the Summer School or Capacity-building Sessions. BIAS will also create special communications for National Labs members, updating them on the impact of their participation and sharing specific initiatives created for them.

LOBA will continue to track and analyse newsletter statistics, including the number of subscribers and unsubscribers, the number of newsletters opened, and the number of clicks.

The mailing lists will be continuously updated, and targeted social media campaigns will be launched to attract more stakeholders to subscribe to BIAS updates. To support this effort, as previously mentioned, a pop-up subscription window will be implemented on the BIAS website to encourage newsletter sign-ups.

7.1.7. Actionable Knowledge

A set of Actionable Knowledge materials (factsheets, infographics, booklets, etc.) will be developed during the third year of the project as more relevant results emerge. These will include:

- Factsheet on “BIAS Co-Creation Workshops: Insights and Results” (D2.4)
- Factsheet on “The Definition of Fairness”
- Booklet on the ALTAI for AI in the Labour Market (preliminary findings – D3.3)
- Series of infographics highlighting key information from the ethnographic work (D4.2)
- Factsheet on the main findings from the Capacity Building sessions (D5.1)

7.1.8. Scientific dissemination

As more results are produced over the next two years of the project, BIAS consortium members will increase the number of scientific articles and papers published in leading journals. Furthermore, LOBA has created a Zenodo account and community for the project, as well as an OpenAIRE account, allowing the project to have a sustainable place where its scientific publications can be available indefinitely. The DOIs of the articles will be included in the OpenAIRE repository.

7.1.9. Activities and events

In addition to the events that will be organised under the project within WP2 (Online Co-creation Workshops), WP5 (Capacity-building Sessions), and WP6 (Summer School), the partners are encouraged to participate in events, conferences and workshops with the purpose of disseminating knowledge of the project activities, create awareness and to communicate the project’s findings and results to a wider group of experts or non-experts.

The events relevant for BIAS’ participation are in the context of AI and NLP, Human Resources, Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), ethics and regulation of AI in HRM, among others.

Project partners are encouraged to monitor relevant events and record their details in an internal spreadsheet designed to track these “future events.” Additionally, during each event, they are encouraged to complete the “Events Leads” Excel sheet, which was created to help track the contacts made by partners during these events.

For the first two years, the partners have reported the participation in 47 events, reaching approximately more than 6,600 people.

Thus, the project’s participation in events during the next two years can be significantly increased, creating a great opportunity for disseminating project findings and results in a more direct manner.

The strategy for the promotion and participation in events will continue to be implemented, with more reminders so partners are aware of what support is available to them.

- **Communication BEFORE the event:**
 - Inform LOBA about the event (Title, date, location, objective, type of participation (speaker, panel, stand, etc), URL...).
 - LOBA uploads the event information on the website.
 - (If applicable) LOBA can design a cover image or banner of the event including save the date, agenda and other images for promoting the speakers, etc.
 - LOBA promotes the event in social media channels.
 - LOBA promotes the event on the AI-on-Demand platform.
 - LOBA includes the event in the Newsletter under “upcoming events” (if the event hasn’t taken place) or creates a personalised email marketing campaign.
 - (If applicable) LOBA sends a press release.
 - LOBA shares the event with BIAS partners, subscribers, other projects/initiatives.
 - Crowdhelix shares the event with the AI Fairness Cluster.
 - Crowdhelix promotes the event on the Trustworthy AI Helix.
 - BIAS project’ partners are requested to disseminate the event through their networks and channels (i.e., emails, sharing BIAS posts in partners’ social media, posting in their own channels, publishing information in their websites, blogs and/or Newsletters, etc.).
- **Communication DURING the event:**
 - Partners are encouraged to send pictures and quotes from the event to LOBA to be posted on social media.
 - Partners conduct networking and distribution of promotional materials.
 - Partners fill in the “Events Leads” Excel.
- **Communication AFTER the event:**
 - Partner sends a brief report with the main outcomes, insights and conclusions from the event and LOBA uploads a news entry with this information to the website. If relevant, this article is also transformed into a paper that can be printed by the partners and brought to events to bring attention to the work done by the BIAS consortium.
 - If the event has been recorded, the partner can send the file to LOBA to be uploaded in YouTube channel, website and published in social media.
 - LOBA includes the event in the Newsletter under “in case you’ve missed it” (if the event has already taken place).

- BIAS project' partners are requested to disseminate the results of the event among their networks and channels (i.e., sharing BIAS posts in social media, posting in their own channels).
- BIAS project' partners should fill in the "D&C Monitor Table" that allows LOBA to track all the important information about the events attended by the consortium and to upload it in the Participants Portal.

7.2. Networking and clustering

7.2.1. Related projects and initiatives

From M24, the BIAS project will continue to focus on joint activities with the AI Fairness Cluster and collaborations with other projects and events on related topics. The following activities have been planned for the coming months:

- A two-day Fairness Cluster conference with sister projects in March 2025, to be held in Barcelona.
- A coding Summer School from April 7-11, 2025, in Tallinn, which will include a CHX networking event (Trustworthy AI Helix Event) along with participation of AI Fairness Cluster (<https://aifairnesscluster.eu/>) Member Projects: AEQUITAS, FINDHR, and MAMMOth.
- Another two-day AI Fairness Cluster conference in October 2025, in Brussels, which will include a CHX networking event and serve as the final conference for AEQUITAS, FINDHR, and MAMMOth.
- Two webinars are planned in collaboration with similar projects. The first is currently being organized with DIVERSIFAIR (<https://www.womeninai.co/>) and is scheduled for December 2024. The second webinar is expected to be delivered by September 2025. The new collaboration opportunities will be established to have the webinar jointly with initiatives/projects focusing on the similar topics as BIAS project. In that sense, AI Fairness Cluster projects will be invited to collaborate as well.

7.2.2. AI Fairness Cluster

The AI Fairness Cluster consists of four European projects: AEQUITAS, BIAS, FINDHR, and MAMMOTH, all funded through the Horizon Europe program. This network plays a key role in the European Commission's strategy to ensure the trustworthiness of AI, with a focus on developing and implementing human-centric, sustainable, secure, inclusive, and trustworthy AI technologies. AI Fairness Cluster's coordinating organization, the BIAS project, is in the position to suggest a strategy

for the cluster's future course. In addition to addressing the present problems with bias in AI, this approach will guarantee that the collaborative network lays the groundwork for long-term, sustainable collaboration across member projects. BIAS is dedicated to make the AI Fairness Cluster a major force in determining Europe's future of reliable AI by creating a common vision, establishing specific goals, and encouraging constant communication.

Addressing the crucial problems of bias, fairness, and transparency in AI systems is the goal of both the AI Fairness Cluster and the BIAS project. The cluster's future plan demonstrates BIAS's dedication to enhancing project collaboration, encouraging creativity, and making sure the EU stays at the forefront of reliable and moral AI. This plan lays out the main steps BIAS will take to further the cluster's objective as follows:

- **Cluster governance:** In order to ensure effective coordination and decision-making among its member projects, BIAS will formally establish the AI Fairness Cluster's governance structure. Cluster activities will be maintained under the direction of BIAS, which will also make sure that they are in line with EU priorities.
- **Thematic events:** To address issues including algorithmic fairness, data openness, bias mitigation and regulations, BIAS will be hosting events/conferences alongside other cluster members. The representatives of the member projects will get together on a regular basis to exchange ideas, coordinate approaches, and make sure that research projects complement one another, eventually plan and implement conferences such as the already under preparation two-day Fairness Cluster conference, scheduled to take place in March 2025 in Barcelona.
- **Policy contributions:** BIAS will be providing recommendations through the cluster to assist the European Commission and other regulatory agencies in putting into practice fair and open AI systems. This will guarantee that the research outputs of the cluster impact the formulation of EU policies on AI systems.
- **Enhancing partnerships:** To increase the influence of the AI Fairness Cluster, BIAS is/will be seeking collaborations during and after the project with business, educational institutions, and civil society groups. BIAS will encourage the adoption of fairness in AI systems in a variety of industries through these partnerships.
- **Sustainability:** The AI Fairness Cluster's long-term viability is a priority for BIAS. This involves looking at funding options once the project is finished, such as through public-private partnerships or related Horizon Europe calls. By encouraging new projects and initiatives to join the cluster, BIAS will take the lead in efforts to grow it and create a vibrant, changing network that consistently tackles fresh issues in AI equity.

7.2.3. Trustworthy AI Helix

CrowdHelix, a partner of the BIAS project, offers a unique platform that connects researchers, experts, RTOs, and SMEs across various fields. Within the BIAS project, CrowdHelix has launched the “Trustworthy AI Helix,” an open innovation community focused on mitigating diversity biases in AI within the labour market. The Helix serves as one of the project's key dissemination tools, allowing stakeholders to access and engage with BIAS' research outputs. This community will continue beyond the project's completion as a self-sustaining entity, facilitating collaborative partnerships. A dedicated Helix Manager (CHX) will oversee onboarding new members, fostering connections among stakeholders, and ensuring ongoing collaboration.

A standout feature of the CrowdHelix platform is its matchmaking algorithm (recommender engine), which enhances the value of both Helixes and registered organizations. This tool matches posted opportunities with researchers and institutions that have the relevant expertise or infrastructure. Once an individual or organization joins the Trustworthy AI Helix and updates their profile, the platform's recommender engine will flag their expertise for suitable opportunities. The matchmaking algorithm will also facilitate connections with key stakeholders and assist in identifying specific collaborators for the project's future needs.

Figure 1: Helix Recommender Engine

To harness and guide this virtual ecosystem, CHX will be organizing two helix events by 2025 and one in 2026 to bring profiled organizations together to discuss topics relevant to both the Helix community and BIAS. Each Helix also hosts topic-specific events and serves as a cross-sector, international collaboration platform, facilitating successful Horizon Europe proposals.

As of M24, the Helix is actively used for the dissemination and exploitation of results, as well as for sharing announcements about project activities. Since its launch in April 2023, the platform has featured **37 collaboration opportunities**, **2 results**, **5 events**, and **3 announcements**. The Helix will continue to be promoted through upcoming Helix Events and joint activities.

7.3. Project and Community Sustainability

7.3.1. Post-project Trustworthy AI Helix maintenance

The Trustworthy AI Helix will serve as the collaborative ecosystem designed to maximize the project’s impact by providing a dedicated platform for the dissemination and exploitation of BIAS results, ultimately enhancing its innovation potential. This virtual community will extend beyond BIAS project partners, encompassing stakeholders interested in utilizing and leveraging the project’s outputs, thereby ensuring long-term sustainability. Crowdhelix is committed to maintaining the Helix for at least two years following the project’s conclusion. After the project ends, the Helix will remain hosted on the CHX platform, allowing all participants who joined during the project to retain their accounts at no cost as external organizations. They will also have the option for their organizations to join as full members of the network, further supporting the enduring impact of the BIAS project.

7.3.2. Funding synergies for exploitation

In collaboration with DigiTouch and LOBA, Crowdhelix is conducting an analysis of future funding opportunities aligned with the project’s objectives to facilitate the market entry of outputs and support the further development of results achieved during the BIAS implementation. The Trustworthy AI Helix will create opportunities for collaboration within the Horizon Europe framework. Crowdhelix will promote the formation of new consortia to leverage the BIAS project and extend its impact beyond the project’s scope. BIAS consortium members will be invited to join new project consortia based on their expertise and willingness to participate. Crowdhelix will facilitate this process by connecting BIAS consortium members with its extensive network and organizing dedicated matchmaking events as part of its internal activities. Additionally, Crowdhelix has maintained a list of funding opportunities to monitor upcoming collaborations; by M23 of the project, a total of 10 opportunities have been identified.

Figure 2: Crowdhelix Model

The BIAS project is actively planning both academic and commercial exploitation of the developed intellectual properties (IP) within Work Package 6 (WP6). Task 6.1 is focused on compiling a comprehensive list of background and potential foreground IP, outlining their pathways to exploitation and commercialization potential. These details will be thoroughly presented in Deliverable D6.1.

This section also summarizes the investment synergies and fundraising roadmap for the commercially exploitable results of the BIAS project. To ensure the sustainability of the innovations developed, the partners, led by DIGI, will pursue additional investments aimed at achieving operational and commercial viability.

Figure 3: Different fund-raising rounds

Typically, the commercialization of innovation involves three types of investments: (a) angel investment, (b) venture capital funding in early rounds, and (c) governmental grants. DIGI plans to utilize a combination of angel investment and government grants to support the initial commercialization of project results. To facilitate this, DIGI will conduct a thorough investment analysis encompassing Internal Rate of Return (IRR), Return on Investment (ROI), and Return on Equity (ROE) in relation to the BIAS project’s business plan. This analysis will assess the maturity of the results, their commercial viability, associated risks, and the potential for raising capital (e.g., seed funding, Series A).

An evaluation of the investor readiness level (IRL) for the BIAS results will be conducted to establish and implement a roadmap aimed at improving the IRL to level 6. Following this assessment, the task will also focus on developing funding synergies with additional financing mechanisms, including the European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF), European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), European Social Fund Plus (ESF+), InvestEU, Just Transition Fund (JTF), and the Digital Europe Programme, as well as opportunities for public funding, angel investing, and venture capital. Below is a non-exhaustive list of angel investors that provide funding for AI and HR-related technologies:

Name	Geographical reach	Website
European Angels Fund (EAF)	EAF is operational across Europe with dedicated national programmes for Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands and Spain alongside a pan-European allocation for Business Angels in other geographies and investing across the continent.	Link
Sofia Angels Ventures	Across Europe	Link
Caesar Business Angels		Link
European Business Angels Network		Link
Change Ventures	Baltic start-up seed fund	Link

Table 3: List of Angel Investors providing funding for AI and HR related technologies

In addition to the investor assessment process, three key partners of the BIAS project—DIGI, Crowdhelix, and LOBA—are leading the "Funding synergies for exploitation" initiative. Each partner brings a distinct set of skills, connections, and resources to ensure that the project's innovations are successfully marketed and widely adopted. This section outlines each partner's specific roles and how they will collaborate on the exploitation strategy.

DIGI:

As a partner with extensive expertise in AI and digital transformation, DIGI will focus on:

- **Technical Exploitation:** DIGI is responsible for ensuring that the BIAS project's technical outputs - such as datasets, AI tools, and algorithms - are refined for commercial use. They will lead the development of exploitable assets, ensuring they are market-ready and compliant with industry standards.
- **Identifying Industry-Specific Use Cases:** DIGI will work closely with sectors like healthcare, finance, and public services to identify key applications where the project's AI fairness solutions can be applied. This involves preparing technical solutions for adoption and tailoring them to specific industries.

Crowdhelix:

With expertise in networking and clustering within research and innovation projects, Crowdhelix contributes to the exploitation strategy through its knowledge of information sharing, network creation, and research-to-market channels. Their key responsibilities include:

- **Engaging Stakeholders and Building Networks:** Crowdhelix will leverage its broad network of industries, SMEs, and research organizations to form partnerships that support the

commercial use of BIAS's results. They will ensure the project's outcomes are relevant to potential users, such as companies looking to implement fair AI systems.

- Knowledge Transfer and Dissemination: Crowdhelix will lead knowledge transfer efforts, ensuring that the public, policymakers, and relevant stakeholders are informed about the project's findings. This will include organizing seminars, webinars, and other events that highlight the value of BIAS's results.
- Collaborating on Exploitation Synergies: Crowdhelix will work closely with LOBA and DIGI to explore potential synergies for exploitation.

LOBA:

LOBA plays a key role in maximizing the visibility of the BIAS project and supporting its exploitation activities. LOBA will maintain the BIAS website for five years after the project is finished. Furthermore, by increasing target stakeholders' awareness and visibility of the BIAS project, dissemination activities will foster conditions for successful exploitation. These efforts will connect with diverse groups through strategic use of the project website, social media, newsletters, and external events, generating interest in the project's outcomes. In addition to showcasing the project's progress, this extensive outreach helps build long-term relationships with potential users and partners, establishing a foundation for successful cross-sector exploitation of project results.

8 Timeline

The following table presents an evaluation of the timeline estimated in D7.1 Dissemination, Exploitation, Communications Plan, against the real implementation. The **blue** colour means the activity has been implemented according to plan, **yellow** means the activity was implemented with some delay, and **red** means the activity was not achieved in the timeframe M1 to M24, being delayed to the next timeframe M25 – M36.

	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
Identity & Brand manual		X										
Stationery (Templates & supporting materials)		X										
Splash Page		X ¹										
Social Media channels		X										
Teaser video		X										
Website					X							
Promotional Materials (Brochure, poster...)					X							
Promotional video							X ²					
1st newsletter							X ³					
Press Release							X					

Table 4: Evaluation of initial timeline set up in D7.1

The following table presents the approximate timeframe for conducting dissemination and communication activities in the third year of the project. The dissemination and communication activities are divided into online and digital dissemination tools (website, social media, press release,

¹ The splash page was launched in March because the consortium was waiting for a final decision from AI4Europe on a potential mandatory guideline to use the AIoD WordPress Theme for website creation.

² The video was originally planned to be released in Month 7 but it was released in Month 8 due to some alterations to the script, illustrations and voice-over.

³ The first newsletter was initially scheduled for release in Month 7 but was delayed until Month 11 because the consortium decided to increase the number of subscribers before distributing the first edition.

newsletter, promotional videos, actionable knowledge) and personal (offline) interaction activities (communication toolkit and events). This timeline is merely indicative, and there is some flexibility in the implementation of these activities, but they shouldn't deviate too much from what is presented here.

Online digital dissemination channels/tools	Indicative Timeline											
	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
Website maintenance	Continuous											
Social Media management	Continuous											
Newsletter	X							X				
Digital dissemination/images	Continuous											
Press Release	Adhoc (when relevant announcement/achievements)											
Interaction activities	Indicative Timeline											
	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
Factsheets and infographics	X			X				X				
Trustworthy AI Helix Events						X						X
AI Fairness Cluster events					X							X
Promotion & participation in external events	Adhoc											
Promotion & support organisation of project activities	Adhoc											

Table 5: Indicative Timeline of Dissemination Activities and Tools M125-M36

9 Conclusions

To effectively meet the primary goals of the Revised Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communications Plan, the BIAS project must present itself as a unified brand with a clear commitment to mitigating AI biases in the labour market. This commitment should be reinforced through a well-coordinated set of communication tools, engaging and relevant content, and a dedicated team of partners.

In the initial phases, significant progress has been made, including the establishment of communication channels and tools, such as the project website, social media presence, and promotional materials. These efforts have successfully enhanced awareness of the project, achieving KPIs and laying a strong foundation for future dissemination activities.

As we transition to the conversion phase, our focus will shift to turning engagement into tangible actions. This includes optimizing our website to facilitate user actions, creating strategic press releases to highlight key achievements, and leveraging social media for targeted campaigns. The social media strategy will feature dynamic Reels and engaging content to drive deeper interaction and conversion.

The upcoming period will be pivotal for advancing the project's dissemination and communication goals. Success will hinge on a strategic, multi-channel approach to sharing content with stakeholders and the broader community. LOBA will play a proactive role in driving these efforts, encouraging all partners to actively contribute and disseminate project insights within their networks.

The updated plan will be dynamic, reflecting ongoing developments and adapting to emerging opportunities as the project progresses. Final outcomes and achievements related to dissemination and communication will be detailed in the project's progress reports to the Commission and in the "Final Report on Dissemination Activities."

BIAS

Mitigating biases
of AI in the
labour market

Consortium

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